

**THE ROLE OF CARTOONS IN EDUCATION CHILDREN'S
GENERATION**

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the educational value, level and popularization of modern animated works. In addition, cartoons that are popular today, their influence on children's consciousness and upbringing, and the opinion of viewers about cartoons were studied.

Keywords: Education, cartoon, psyche, psychology, mentality.

**BARKAMOL AVLOD TARBIYASIDA ANIMATSION FILMLARNING
O'RNI**

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ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqolada bugungi kundagi multfilm asarlarining tarbiyaviy ahamiyati, saviyasi va targ'iboti hususida fikr yuritiladi. Bundan tashqari, bugungi kundagi

tomoshabinbop multfilmlar, ularning bolalar ongiga va tarbiyasiga ta'siri va multfilmlar haqida teletomoshabinlarning fikrlari o'rganib chiqildi.

Kalit so'zlar: Tarbiya, multfilm, psixika, psixologiya, mintalitet.

РОЛЬ МУЛЬТФИЛЬМОВ В ВОСПИТАНИИ ДЕТСКОГО ПОКОЛЕНИЯ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматривается воспитательное значение, уровень и популяризация современных мультипликационных произведений. Кроме того, были изучены популярные сегодня мультфильмы, их влияние на детское сознание и воспитание, мнение телезрителей о мультфильмах.

Ключевые слова: Образование, мультфильм, психика, психология, менталитет.

Entrance

Youth education has always been one of the most important tasks for any society. Especially in today's era of globalization, we are all concerned that the age-old traditions of our people in terms of education, based on unique and appropriate national and religious values, are losing their true essence under the influence of "mass culture", ideas and views foreign to our mentality. If we do not pay serious attention to this process, in terms of the issue of education, it may be too late tomorrow and cause irreparable

consequences. After all, we should never forget the words of the well-known enlightener Abdulla Awlani, "Education for us is a matter of either life or death, or salvation - or destruction, or happiness - or disaster."

On June 15, Shavkat Mirziyoyev spoke at the conference on the topic "Ensuring social stability, preserving the purity of our holy religion - the need of the times" in Tashkent.

"Another important issue that always worries us is the manners, behavior, and worldview of our youth. Today, our era is changing rapidly. We see these changes more than anyone. "Who feels these changes the most - of course, - the youth". Let the youth be in harmony with the demands of their time. But at the same time, let them not forget their own identity. The call of who we are and what kind of great people we are is always echoing in their hearts. "Let them encourage them to stay true to themselves. How can we achieve this? Education, education and only education," says President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev.

METHODS

While describing the image of an educated, enlightened, mature person, Farabi, says: "Whoever wants to learn wisdom, let him start at a young age, let him be healthy, have good morals and manners, let him speak his word on time according to his/her promise and appropriate way. May he succeed, may he be protected from bad deeds, may he know all the laws and regulations, may he be knowledgeable and eloquent, may he respect learned and wise people, may he not spare his world from knowledge and people of knowledge, have knowledge of all real material things".

Bu fikrlardan **Farobiyning** ta'lim – tarbiyada yoshlarni mukammal inson qilib tarbiyalashda xususan, aqliy – axloqiy tarbiyada aloxida e'tibor berganligi ko'rinib turibdi, uning e'tiqodicha, bilim, ma'rifat, albatta yaxshi axloq bilan bezatmog'i lozim, aks holda kutilgan maqsadga erishilmaydi, bola yetuk bo'lib yetishmaydi.

Looking through at our present day, I think it is appropriate to dwell on the issue of raising children. How are children growing up today? How unhealthy family environment, inattention and indifference affect today's children? What do they do in

their spare time? Why is crime observed among teenagers? What are the big momentum for them to mobilisation and happen such kind of cruel crimes? Isn't the influence of the virtual world the cause of all this?

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

When we look at the childrens of today, we can easily notice that they are sitting in front of the television and watching cartoons most of the time before they know their mindset and mind. Especially, most of them will be Musical cartoons, not based on any reality. Of course, these are international cartoons, because among our national cartoons, we still do not find works created for children. An example of this is the cartoon "Baby Shark", which is the favorite of all children. And at this point, we will mention the following news. USA prison inmate died after being tortured to the tune of the popular children's song Baby Shark.

Well, let's talk about not babies, but also, about children whose knowledge potential has begun to develop. They can easily find and watch their favorite cartoons on YouTube. And of course, their favorite cartoons are world cartoons.

When we were young, we grew up with our favorite cartoons like "Tom and Jerry", "Mickey Mouse", "Donald Duck". But in today's rapidly developing world, the modern themes of world cartoons are also expanding. We have no objection to this, but it goes back to again our "national mentality".

CONCLUSION

When we are creating cartoons, if we try to look at these works not as a means of having fun, but as a means of education we would have paid attention in an appropriate way to the education of young people. No matter how high-quality, high-technological cartoons are created, they retain their educational significance and arouse positive emotions in the minds of young viewers.

Let's continue our thoughts in the framework of children's psychology and the influence of cartoons on children's psychology. Here, of course, we will give an example of the thoughts of Dilobar Rasulova, an expert in psychology, practicing psychologist, in an interview with the reporter of the "Khalk sozi" newspaper.

"Certain cartoons which are shown on television have a negative impact on the child's development and psyche. They form aggression, irritability and mental disorders in children. Based on this, parents should control the time the child spends in front of the TV. However, one thing should always be kept in mind. This is not to say that all cartoons are harmful. Among the cartoons, there are also meaningful ones that develop the personality...

A few decades ago, cartoons were broadcast only after passing strict control, every frame of cartoons was checked. Many cartoons such as "Three Brothers and Sisters", "Stories of Uncle Beaver", "Tales of the Brothers Grimm" have a beneficial effect on the child's psyche, teach children to be kind and orderly. But most parents today consider such cartoons to be old and boring. Examples of cartoons with a positive effect are "Alpomish", "Zumrad va Qimmat", "Spitomen", "Kenja botir", which promote our national values.

There are many cartoons that have a negative effect on the development of the child's psyche and intelligence. Due to such cartoons, children often have wrong understanding about values, life, friends and parents. Under the influence of cartoons, children offer negative and aggressive games. Cartoons show a lot of violence and brutality. The scenes of blood, fights, and etc should not be shown to the children. Children can then imitate their favorite characters and become cruel, or such footage can lead to childhood fears and isolation.

And in some cartoons, men have feminine features and vice versa. These signs are especially reflected in their clothing and behavior. This also leads to the formation of wrong concepts in children.

On screen, you can often see disrespect for animals and plants, the elderly and parents. Children memorize all this and try to repeat those actions.

"Everyone knows the cartoon "Masha and the Bear", it quickly became popular. However, this animation has a negative effect on children. The cartoon embodies the image of a cheerful girl who laughs at the elderly. In it, a young and cheerful girl is depicted as Masha, and an old one is depicted as a bear. "The big personality is

embodied, in a sense. This is a cartoon that has a psychological effect on the developing values of the children of Eastern countries."

It is an obvious fact that cartoons affect the child's nervous system without any means. In 1997, 653 children in Japan were hospitalized due to epileptic seizures. When the situation was investigated, it was caused by an episode in the 38th episode of the cartoon "Pokemon". On this day, all the children watched that scene over and over again. The cartoon was later banned by the Japanese government and was never remade. Shavkat Kholdorov, who returned from studying at the Tokyo University of Agriculture and Technology, told about the current situation in Japan and an interesting way of bringing animated films to the people:

"In Japan, there is an interesting custom not to 'stick' a child to the screen. After showing the newly produced films and focusing everyone's attention on them, the broadcast on the TV channel will be stopped, and the rest will be printed in the form of books. The sequels of the cartoons, which are watched by adults, can be read and learned as a family in the form of books. Those who are interested in the fate of their favorite heroes eagerly await the next editions of the work. In this, both reading and the art of creating animated films will develop together," says Shavkat Khaldorov.

The owners of this industry cite a good script, funding and personnel problems as to why the multiplication industry is not developing in Uzbekistan. But animator and director Abdulatif Haydarov, who founded a private animation studio in 2016, said he had a different opinion.

"True, the three factors you mentioned are our main weakness. But everything does not always depend on this. Money will be allocated. For example, let it be 1 million. Only sixty percent of it is spent on the main work. Forty percent is taxed by the state and taken back again. If this amount is given in full, who wouldn't work hard! There are also screenwriters. There are many who write really well. That's a pity, there are also people who kill your frustration and return what you wrote, not pass the board!

Being paid a pittance for a work of art written with great passion and ideas will dampen anyone's enthusiasm. As for the personnel, this is not a big problem either. I

know Uzbeks who work for foreign companies. Get paid per second. The advantage of this field is that you can work comfortably at home. I know such masters of their work, if necessary, I cannot pay the fee they ask. Because he knows his professionalism, he wants to be paid accordingly. He does it right. Everyone should be able to live up to their work," says Abdulatif Haydarov.

In our cartoons, we can observe that they are made from Uzbek folk tales, which can serve as an example in terms of ideas. There is an idea and funds, a cartoon was created and broadcast. We will turn to the people again and learn their opinions about these cartoons.

"Not only my children, but also myself are bored with the cartoons produced by Uzbekkino." In my opinion, cartoons should be full of events, colorful, with a sharp subject, beautiful pictures and high quality. It would be very interesting and good if more historical and fantastic films were made. And recommendations can be given through historical cartoons. My son is Japanese, and my little daughter loves to watch western cartoons. They don't see ours as low-quality, their characters are artificial, not human-like," said Marhabo Jorayeva, a mother of four children.

If we dwell on this topic, there are a lot of ideas, a lot of issues that need to be . There are many tasks that we need to do in practice, not just in words. We also want to have our own national product, our works that can be seen again and again. And this is certainly the duty of each industry representative. After all, the best investment is for our children, for their education and future!

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